

Significance of Minimum Ionising Potentials of Gases in Relation to their Molecular Volumes.

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The displacement of an electron of any atom from its orbit in the stable condition is always associated with a certain amount of energy. Unless this amount exceeds a certain minimum value the atoms do not in general gain in energy. For the energy corresponding to $h\nu$, the atoms, however, just gain in energy and the electron is displaced from its most stable orbit to an unstable one, ν , being the frequency of the first member of the absorption series, which is re-emitted in again falling back to the stable orbit. In this case, as can be seen, the electron is not driven to the extreme orbit of the atom or beyond the range of nuclear attraction. The energy corresponding to $h\nu$, where ν , is the convergence frequency of the series for which ν , is of the first member, gives the necessary energy for the atoms to be ionised and is known as ionisation potential, the term $h\nu$, being called resonance potential by Tate and Foote.

According to the electron theory, the electric doublet formed by the displacement of an electron relative to the central core, under the influence of an external electric field explains the polarisation of a medium. Considering the electron displacements in the case of the polarised media to be the same as in the cases of those by the absorption of minimum energy $h\nu$, Compton (*Phys. Review*, 1916, 8, 412) has shown that the natural frequency

$$\nu_r = \frac{1}{\pi} \sqrt{\frac{\pi N e^2}{m(K-1)}}$$

N being the number of molecules per unit volume, e and m the charge and mass of the electron, and K the dielectric constant.

If V_r is the minimum ionising potential,
then $e.V_r = h\nu_r$,

$$\text{or } V_r = \frac{300h}{\pi e} \sqrt{\frac{\pi N e^2}{m(K-1)}} .$$

Substituting the known values of constants e , m and h ,

$$V_r = \frac{.194}{\sqrt{K-1}}$$

The calculated values of V_r , i.e., minimum or resonance potentials are in good agreement with experimental values. The value of K was derived from refractive index for infinite wave-length.

Di-electric Constant and the Molecular Volume.

On the modern belief of the structure of matter as presupposed in this calculation, the ring of electron or electrons in rapid orbital motion, constituting the outermost electron shell has been substituted for Mosotti's conducting sphere, and there is reason to believe that the radius of the displaced orbit under the influence of any external field must be greater than the calculated radius of Mosotti. That there is an appreciable field of force outside the outermost shell and it is due to this—that in an elastic collision between any two gas molecules, the separation is greater than the sum of their respective radii—has already been recognised by Jeans to explain the discrepancy between Mosotti's values and those from gas laws (Jeans, "Mathematical Theory of Electricity and Magnetism," 3rd Edition, p. 133). It naturally strikes then, that the first resonance potentials which measure the work done in displacing an electron from the normal orbit to an orbit within the atom further removed from the nucleus must have some reference to the molecular volumes deduced from kinetic theory of gases. This expectation is realised to a certain extent in the Table I, column (IV) which shows that the product of molecular volume v and the

minimum potential V , is a constant quantity within 5 to 6%
The molecular volume is calculated from the equation

$$v = \frac{b}{4} = \frac{1}{32} \times \frac{\theta_0^3}{273\pi_0} z$$

where b is the well known constant of equation of state, θ_0 , and π_0 , being critical temperatures and pressures.

TABLE I.

I Gases.	II Molecular volumes.	III Minimum ionising pot. (volts).	IV $V \times b$.
H ₂	119	10.4 ¹ , 10.2 ¹¹	1236
He	105.0 } 99.51 }	19.7 ¹²	1360
Ne	76	16.84, ⁶ 16.6 ¹²	1261.6
A	144	8.22 ¹⁰ } 11.8 ± .211 }	1186 } 1655 }
Kr	177	6.72 ¹⁰ } 9.7 ¹¹ }	1189 } 1734.6 }
Xe	228	5.27 ¹⁰ } 8.3 ¹¹ }	1204 } 1869.6 }
Ne	1651 } 176 }	7.5 ¹² , 7.4 ¹¹	1237.5
CO	178	7.85, ¹⁰ 7.2, ⁹ 7.4 ¹¹	1281.6
O ₂	142	8.4, ⁹ 9.0 ¹⁰	1278.0
C ₂ H ₄	952	5.1 ¹⁰	1290
F ₂	130 (Cal.)	9.84 ⁹	1270
Cl ₂	252 } 205 }	4.95 ⁹ } 8.2 ¹¹ }	1247 } 1681 }
HCl	182 } 173 }	6.5 ⁹ } 9.3 ¹¹ }	1182 } 1608.9 }
H ₂ O	186 } 160 }	8.64, ⁹ 7.6 ⁹	1175

I Gases.	II Molecular volumes.	III Minimum ionising pot. (volts)	IV $V \times b$
NH ₃	165	7.2	1188
CH ₄	191 } 162†)	6.54° } 9.48 ¹¹ ††)	1242 } 1526 }
NO	198	9.38 ¹¹	1200.6
P ₂ (vapour)	...	5.89°	...
S ₂ (vapour)	364 (Cal.)	4.8°	1270
SO ₂	247	5.85°	1259
CO ₂	191	6.47,° 7.2°	1236
N ₂ O	198	6.26 ¹⁰	1219
CS ₂	343†	3.57°	1243

† Molecular Volumes : Pease, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 43, 991.

†† Molecular Volumes of He, N, H₂O, CH₄, HCl, SO₂, CS₂; Kaye and Laby's Tables.

¹ "Origin of Spectra," Foote and Mohler, Edn. 1922 pp. 68, 74-77.

² Dejardin, *Ann. Physik*, 1924, 2 (X), 241.

³ Hertz and Kloppers, *Zeit. Physik*, 1925, 31, 468.

⁴ Franck and Hertz, *Deut. Phys. Ges.*, 1913, (Jan. 30), p. 34.

⁵ Horton and Davis, *Phil. Mag.*, 1921, 31, 921.

⁶ Compton, *loc. cit.*, p. 415.

⁷ Brandt, *Zeit Physik*, 1921, 8, 32; "Origin of Spectra," p. 190.

⁸ Lockrow, *Astrophys. J.*, 1926, 63, 205.

⁹ Franck-Jordan, "Quantum Sprungen," p. 285.

¹⁰ Calculated by Compton's formula using K from Kaye and Laby's Tables, p. 84.

¹¹ Hughes and Dixon, *Phys. Review*, 1917, 10, 495.

¹² These values for minimum ionising potentials as calculated by Compton (*loc. cit.*) appear to be too low. It may be noted that these values may be obtained as exact differences between first excitation potentials recorded by Dejardin and Hertz and the third inflection points noted by Dejardin for these respective gases at $19 \pm .5$; $15.5 \pm .2$; $13 \pm .5$ (*loc. cit.*).

N. B. Excepting for He these values seem to be one and a half times greater than the corresponding values calculated by Compton. Thus the products $V \times b$ (col. IV) as noted against these values are also found greater,

Analysis of Molecular Volumes with regard to the Structure of Atoms.

The foregoing results can be shown to be quite in accordance with the structure of elements and compounds as suggested by Langmuir (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, 41, 868, 1543). Elements and compounds having the same number and arrangements of electrons in the outer layer but differing only in the magnitude and distribution of nuclear charges have been called by Langmuir as 'Iso-Steres.' In this sense and also in similarity of physical properties N_2 and CO , N_2O and CO_2 , are found iso-steric on analysis of their minimum ionising potentials.

NO having eleven sheath electrons, Langmuir suggests that the structure is the same as that given for nitrogen molecule, the extra electron being imprisoned in the "octet comprising the shell." N_2 , O_2 , F_2 have got similar structures—that of a double neon and therefore their minimum ionising potentials also seem to be halves that of neon. Thus though the critical constants of F_2 are unknown, it seems probable to allot for it a co-volume term (b) very nearly 120. Pease (*loc. cit.*) has calculated the molecular volume of nuclear carbon atom of ethane, with which elementary Fl_2 is iso-steric, to be about 118. Similarly P_2 , S_2 , Cl_2 should have the same structure as of a double argon with half the minimum potential values of it. Value for P_2 seems to be very high. Co-volume term for sulphur is calculated to be 264 which seems to be justifiable on the basis of the known molecular volumes of Cl_2 and thus of double argon atom. The computed values of F_2 and sulphur can also be checked thus: on the knowledge of the structures of neon and argon or neon-like and argon-like elements it is expected that double the difference between the molecular volumes of F_2 and neon should equal to that of Cl_2 and A . Similarly double the difference in molecular volume of oxygen and neon should equal that of sulphur and argon.

Again, elementary sulphur and sulphur dioxide having the same number of disposable electrons seem to be iso-steric, and have approximately the same molecular volume and consequently the same structures. The arrangement of sheath electrons in the cases of SO_2 and S_2 seems to be the same as in the cases of CO and N_2 ; only with this difference that in the former cases there is one neon structure in excess, thus—

$$b_{CO} + b_{Ne} = b_{SO}$$

This coincidence lends support to the view of Pease (*loc. cit.*) that instead of CO and N₂ having condensed structure as Langmuir believed they may have a more general acetylenic structure *i.e.*, 2 octets sharing three pairs of electrons, as is common to these cases. It must not be forgotten however that sulphur dioxide is a polar molecule whereas sulphur is non-polar. Yet their contributions to change the molecular volume or minimum ionising potentials appear very small. Exactly in the same way carbon disulphide has the same number of sheath electrons as CO₂ and N₂O, and it may be reasonable to attribute the same outer structure to CS₂ and as CO₂ and N₂O have, with this modification that there should be two complete neon structures in the interior of carbon disulphide. Thus—

$$b_{CS_2} = 2b_{Ne} + b_{CO_2}$$

HCl, H₂O, NH₃, CH₄ have again the same number of disposable electrons whereas the number of atoms to act as nuclei are 2, 3, 4 and 5 respectively. Without distinguishing, in any very principal part, polar structures of HCl, H₂O and NH₃ from non-polar CH₄ it may be mentioned that sheath electrons are arranged in the same way or that

$$b_{H_2O} + b_{Ne} - b_{HCl} = b_{NH_3} - b_{H_2O} = b_{CH_4} - b_{NH_3}$$

is a constant, for one atom of hydrogen being in excess in each case.

Attempt to a Theoretical Interpretation.

On the assumption that electron is rigidly connected to central charge, the orbital energy of rotation of the electron becomes $\frac{1}{2} I \omega^2$ where I is the moment of inertia and ω the angular velocity of rotation of the electron (Richardson, "Electron Theory of Matter," Edn. 1916, p. 366). It is admitted that the energy necessary to remove an electron from an atom is equal to "its own kinetic energy" and that the energy corresponding to minimum ionising or resonance potential must necessarily be proportional to it. Thus then

$$I \omega^2 \propto h \nu,$$

$$\propto e. V, \text{ (Einstein's Law.)}$$

$$\text{or } \omega^2 \propto \nu,$$

The centrifugal force of the revolving electron which is proportional to x^2/R (where x is the linear velocity of the electron moving in an orbit of radius R) must be balanced by the electrostatic attraction between electron and the central charge in the stable orbit.

$$\text{or } x^2/R = \omega^2 R \propto \frac{1}{KR^2} \quad \text{or } \omega^2 \propto \frac{1}{KR^2} \text{ i.e. } v, \propto \frac{1}{KR^2}$$

As for all gaseous media K is very nearly equal to unity,

v , becomes proportional to $1/v$ or $V, \propto 1/v$

Conclusion.

From the results of column (IV) it appears that $v \propto \sqrt{K-1}$ is in contrast to Landolt's equation stating $\sqrt{k-1/d}$ is constant, or to Lorentz, Mosotti equation $K-1/(K+2)d$ is constant. The present equation also shows that $V, /d$ is constant, which states therefore that the specific work required to displace an electron measured by the minimum ionising potentials or more properly the specific minimum ionising potentials for different gases may be calculated which should have the same significance as Lorentz equation.

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